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A Comprehensive Review of the People's Republic of China's Talent Procurement Programs

Abstract

On April 28th, 2025, former Harvard chemistry professor Charles Lieber took on a new job at Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School in the People's Republic of China, holding the highest faculty rank at the school. This comes four years after his arrest and conviction on charges of lying to US authorities about his ties to the PRC and he is one of the most prominent individuals associated with the PRC's talent procurement programs. Such instances are a part of longstanding initiatives for China to bring talented individuals and critical property from abroad to develop whatever industries and professions that the Chinese Communist Party deems necessary for the PRC's national interest. This article is a comprehensive literature review of Chinese talent procurement programs, compiling both Chinese and Western sources on the subject matter. This review assesses the means by which talent procurement is conducted, the efficacy of such programs, and level of insider threat that these programs pose to national security. While ultimately unsuccessful on a large scale, understanding the execution of this program, as well as US government responses to them, promises to yield valuable lessons regarding insider threat in industrial and military settings, an issue that will only grow in scope and severity as technology and the Great Power Competition continues to escalate.

Keywords: Education; Espionage; Foreign Intelligence; Talent Management; Vulnerability

Introduction

On April 28th, 2025, former Harvard chemistry professor Charles Lieber took on a new job at Tsinghua Shenzhen International Graduate School in the People's Republic of China, holding the highest faculty rank at the school. This comes four years after his arrest and conviction on charges of lying to US authorities about his ties to the PRC and he is one of the most prominent individuals associated with the PRC's talent procurement programs.¹ The PRC's recruitment of those living outside of China with specialized skillsets is well established. In 2008, the PRC launched the Thousand Talents Program (TTP) in a bid to reverse the brain drain that occurred in previous decades and is now one of hundreds of the PRC's talent plans.² These initiatives constitute a source of insider threat for industry, academia, and the US government as they have become a mechanism for illicit knowledge transfer and IP theft.

The body of literature on the PRC's talent plans is extremely broad, and this article will provide a comprehensive review of the Thousand Talents Program and similar initiatives. To this end, the article considers English and Chinese language sources and evaluates the literature in three main categories: methods by which the talent programs are pursued, the actual efficacy of the programs themselves, and the level of threat, real and perceived, that these programs pose to the United States, its allies, and its partners. Understanding and evaluating this dimension of human espionage promises to yield valuable lessons on insider threat, especially as the countries of the world simultaneously become more intertwined through technology and globalization and divided with the formation of blocs and spheres of influence.

Talent Procurement Methodology

The mechanisms of Chinese talent recruitment are convoluted, and a significant part of the literature explores how it is conducted. While Chinese laws, regulations, and guidelines on talent recruitment methodology are not lacking, they detail processes that are vaguely defined and inherently complex. This in conjunction with the enforced secrecy that the PRC imposed on talent recruitment plans has made it difficult to assess the actual methods which are consistently employed. Sources from the West are preoccupied with unpacking the nuances behind the execution of these talent procurement initiatives, with a general

¹William C. Mao and Veronica H. Paulus, "Ex-Harvard Chemist Charles Lieber Joins Chinese University," *The Harvard Crimson*, May 5, 2025, <https://www.thecrimson.com/article/2025/5/5/charles-lieber-china-professorship/>.

²Ellen Barry and Gina Kolata, "China's Lavish Funds Lured U.S. Scientists. What Did It Get in Return?" *The New York Times*, February 6, 2020, <https://www.nytimes.com/2020/02/06/us/chinas-lavish-funds-lured-us-scientists-what-did-it-get-in-return.html>.; "Chinese Talent Plans Encourage Trade Secret Theft, Economic Espionage," Federal Bureau of Investigation, <https://www.fbi.gov/investigate/counterintelligence/the-china-threat/chinese-talent-plans>.

consensus on the CCP's broad criteria for recruitment and general options for pursuing these professionals, given the sheer number and variety of the talent programs.

At the onset of these programs, the CCP established a "Central Coordinating Group on Talent" which maintains oversight over all of the talent programs and sets baseline requirements, procedures, accountability, and a national level agenda. Talent programs fell under the jurisdiction of a myriad of agencies and ministries, all with overlapping and competing interests, and so the creation of the CCGT would allow the CCP to better execute talent procurement.³ Under the umbrella of the CCGT would include the PRC's Ministry of Science and Technology, Ministry of Education, State-Owned Assets Supervision and Administration Commission, the Ministry of Human Resources and Social Security, the People's Bank of China, State Administration of Foreign Experts Affairs, the Chinese Academy of Engineering, the Chinese Academy of Sciences, the Natural Science Foundation, and the Ministry of Culture. The involvement of so many government entities reflect a holistic approach that the PRC is taking to talent cultivation, requiring these many organizations to assemble and distribute funds for scientific research, business enterprises, and cultural development.⁴ The CCGT would schedule the plans like the Thousand Talents Program for five-to-ten-year iterations, budgeting millions in RMB per recruit. These monetary allocations would go towards providing funding for recruits to use on research as well as facilitating an easier transition to living and working in the PRC, notorious for its bureaucratic red tape that would otherwise discourage both foreigners and overseas Chinese from living in China.⁵ The biggest impediments to living in China would be the cumbersome process of registration for housing in favorable areas along with the difficulties of raising a family in China.⁶ With these factors in mind, talent programs also have part-time agreements where an expert need not live in China, but does take time in the

³David Zweig and Wang Huiyao, "Can China Bring Back the Best? The Communist Party Organizes China's Search for Talent," *The China Quarterly*, no. 215 (2013): 590–615, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23510804>, p. 596.

⁴Organization Department of the CPC Central Committee [中共中央组织部], "Measures for the Management of the National Overseas High-level Talent Introduction Program [国家海外高层次人才引进计划管理办法]," Central Committee of the Communist Party of China [中共中央], February 24, 2017, https://www.hunan.gov.cn/xxgk/wjk/zcfgk/202007/t20200730_d9036c3d-58d6-40c5-a3ec-1c3a23f40992.html#:~:text=%E7%AC%AC%E4%B8%80%E6%9D%A1%20%E5%9B%BD%E5%A%E%B6.

⁵Zweig and Wang, "Can China Bring Back the Best? The Communist Party Organizes China's Search for Talent," p. 602, 604.

⁶Stephanie Segal and Dylan Gerstel. "China's Strategy to Become an Innovation Leader," in *Research Collaboration in an Era of Strategic Competition*, Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), 2019, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep22585>, p. 6.

year to work for PRC institutions, or at the very least, facilitate partnerships between Chinese and foreign organizations.⁷

While the PRC pursues recruiting foreign citizens as part of its Foreign Thousand Talents Program, the majority of the talent plans are focused on convincing Chinese citizens living overseas and ethnic Chinese citizens of other countries to come work for the PRC. The reason being is that ethnic Chinese would better adapt to the peculiarities of life in China, and the CCGT explicitly instructed recruiters to make appeals based on a shared cultural heritage and the prospect of esteem from people in the greater Chinese community.⁸ The preference for Chinese nationals who have moved abroad becomes especially clear given the fact that non-Chinese experts cannot apply for several of these talent procurement programs themselves. These programs require Chinese companies, universities, or research institutes to identify individuals of interest and apply for the talent programs on behalf of the non-Chinese nationals that they wish to recruit.⁹

The guidance provided by the national government for pursuing these talent plans is broad, with general criteria for the Thousand Talents Program being that potential recruits be no older than 55 years of age, must work in China for longer than six months as part of their contract, and should have doctoral or advanced degree from a credible university abroad.¹⁰ They must also have one or more of the following: relevant experience in a research capacity at a major university abroad, over three years in advanced technical or executive experience at a prominent financial or business institution abroad, unique intellectual or

⁷Original CSET Translation of "2019 Chinese Academy of Sciences Talent Program Application Guide" [2019 年度中国科学院人才项目申报指南], Chinese Academy of Sciences, June 30, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/2019-chinese-academy-of-sciences-talent-program-application-guide>; Elsa B. Kania, "Testimony before the House Permanent Select Committee on Intelligence," Center for a New American Security, July 19, 2018, <https://www.cnas.org/publications/congressional-testimony/testimony-before-the-house-permanent-select-committee-on-intelligence>, p. 10-12.

⁸Zweig and Wang, "Can China Bring Back the Best? The Communist Party Organizes China's Search for Talent," p. 600.

⁹Original CSET Translation of "Notice Declaring the 2019 High-End Foreign Expert Recruitment Plan" [科技部办公厅关于申报 2019 年度高端外国专家引进计划的通知], PRC Ministry of Science and Technology, March 17, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/notice-of-the-office-of-the-ministry-of-science-and-technology-declaring-the-2019-high-end-foreign-expert-recruitment-plan/>; Original CSET Translation of "Notice on Applying for 2020 National Foreign Expert Projects" [关于申报 2020 年度国家外国专家项目的通知], International Exchange and Approval Office, February 13, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/notice-on-applying-for-2020-national-foreign-expert-projects/>.

¹⁰Hanna Kim and Ryan Michael Allen, "Globalizing cures for China's brain drain ills: The Thousand Talents Plan in Shanghai, Tianjin, and Guangdong," *International Journal of Comparative Education and Development*, Vol. 20 Issue: 1 (2018): 16-32, <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJCED-10-2017-0028>, p. 19.

business property set for expansion, and/or have potential startup with focus on the needs of the PRC.¹¹ These particular needs are generally in STEM, and include emerging fields that have military utility such as semiconductors, energy development, and biotechnology.¹² As the PRC's Military-Civil Fusion plan to boost the People's Liberation Army's modernization became increasingly important, more talent recruitment efforts were aimed at facilitating work on strategic and emerging disciplines, with the Chinese Academy of Sciences aiming to have foreign scientists work for them at least part-time.¹³ As time progressed however, in 2017, guidelines for talent recruitment would now also include experts in philosophy and social sciences, with an additional emphasis on cultural and artistic talents.¹⁴

The talent programs in the PRC operate in four tiers: national, provincial, city, and institutional.¹⁵ Despite having a national agenda for the talent programs, the execution of these plans are somewhat decentralized, with each locale tailoring their approaches to maximize what their unique locale can offer. Following the introduction of the Thousand Talents Program and other related plans (hereafter jointly referred to as TTB or Thousand Talents Brand), cities all over China held meetings to set their own recruitment goals and a timeline for achieving them. This was done based on the city's needs and their actual ability to accommodate the talented scholars. Beijing for instance, with its Zhongguancun Science Park, set an ambitious goal of 500 recruits, while the lesser-known Jinan set a goal of 150 scholars.¹⁶ The cities also marketed themselves differently, and customized the awards to scholars in the program accordingly. For instance, Shanghai with its commercial history, also sought entrepreneurs in addition to scientists, while Guangzhou made specific overtures to Cantonese speaking Chinese living overseas, hoping that its proximity to Hong Kong would facilitate a strong network of experts.¹⁷ In 2017, there was also mention of

¹¹Ibid., p. 20.

¹²US Senate Staff, "Threats to the U.S. Research Enterprise: China's Talent Recruitment Plans," United States Senate Permanent Subcommittee on Investigations, 2019, <https://research.unc.edu/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/osr-Senate-HSGAC-Subcommittee-Full-Report.pdf>, p. 17.

¹³Original CSET Translation of "2019 Chinese Academy of Sciences Talent Program Application Guide" [2019 年度中国科学院人才项目申报指南].

¹⁴Organization Department of the CPC Central Committee [中共中央组织部], "Measures for the Management of the National Overseas High-level Talent Introduction Program [国家海外高层次人才引进计划管理办法]."

¹⁵Zhu Junwen, "The Composition and Evolution of China's High-Level Talent Programs in Higher Education," *ECNU Review of Education*, 2(1), 104-110, April 2, 2019, <https://doi.org/10.1177/2096531119840869>.

¹⁶Zweig and Wang, "Can China Bring Back the Best? The Communist Party Organizes China's Search for Talent," p. 601.

¹⁷Kim and Allen, "Glocalizing cures for China's brain drain ills: The Thousand Talents Plan in Shanghai, Tianjin, and Guangdong," p. 21-22, 24-25.

special programs exclusively for Xinjiang and Tibet, two of the PRC's poorest provinces and subject of significant controversy and instability in the PRC.¹⁸

Once potential recruits have been identified, talent recruitment stations in other countries will reach out to the expert in question to offer rewards and honors as a part of the TTB. These talent recruitment stations are housed in buildings belonging to various Chinese venture capital firms, ostensibly “non-government organizations,” and global diaspora organizations.¹⁹ These myriad groups are termed Chinese professional associations. While many operate independent from CCP influence and provide networking and social support services to overseas Chinese, others serve as access points to Chinese labs and state-owned enterprises. Many of these professional associations do not hide the fact that they are affiliated with Chinese talent procurement, with 61% professing on their websites that they are involved in these programs.²⁰ An example of most well-known of such organizations are the Confucius Institutes, many of which have offices at universities overseas.²¹ Other means of drawing the attention of foreign experts, particularly those who are not Chinese, and therefore have no ties to professional organizations include exhibitions, conferences, or even utilizing coworkers who are affiliated with the TTB.²² Once sufficiently interested and in communication with those running the talent programs, a prospective recruit would then be presented with a contract detailing the terms of being a member of a program falling under the TTB.

¹⁸Organization Department of the CPC Central Committee [中共中央组织部], “Measures for the Management of the National Overseas High-level Talent Introduction Program [国家海外高层次人才引进计划管理办法].”

¹⁹Jeffrey Stoff, “Reassessing Threats to US Innovation Posed by China and Implications for Safeguarding Future Supply Chains,” Redcliff Enterprises, June 9, 2022, https://www.uscc.gov/sites/default/files/2022-06/Jeff_Stoff_Testimony.pdf, p. 14.

²⁰Ryan Fedasiuk and Emily Weinstein, “Overseas Professionals and Technology Transfer to China,” Center for Security and Emerging Technology, July 21, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/overseas-professionals-and-technology-transfer-to-china/>.

²¹Cameron Keen, “Academic Espionage: How International Trade Law Can Protect Higher Education,” *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law*, Vol. 49, no. 1, 213-239, <https://digitalcommons.law.uga.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2506&context=gjicl#:~:text=iious%20research%20activities%20conducted%20in%20China.38>, p. 217-218.

²²Majdi Alghader, “THE THREAT OF FOREIGN INFLUENCE ON THE U.S. ACADEMIC RESEARCH AND NATIONAL SECURITY: CURRENT TRENDS, BEST PRACTICES, AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS,” John Hopkins University Scholarship Library, December 2023, <https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/c6df502f-a7ec-4ab0-bb03-f08d46bfa4b1/content>, p. 42; Original CSET Translation of “Program to Build a National Technology Transfer System” [国务院关于印发国家技术转移体系建设方案的通知], Central People’s Government of the People’s Republic of China, November 29, 2019, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/program-to-build-a-national-technology-transfer-system/>.

An additional variation of the TTB talent recruitment programs also includes the funding of overseas scholarships for undergraduate and postgraduate Chinese and foreign students with the contractual promise that these students would one day work in the PRC for at least two years.²³ These programs are run by the China Scholarship Council, with around 12% of foreign students in China and about 7% of Chinese students studying abroad receive funding from the CSC. Specifically in the US, it is estimated that around 7% of Chinese students receive CSC funding. Such programs, like the traditional TTB programs, take advantage of students in cooperative training programs between foreign universities and Chinese research institutions, circumnavigating US export controls and are affiliated with China's military-industrial base.²⁴

Efficacy of the Talent Procurement Programs

In the years that follow the introduction of the talent procurement initiatives, both Chinese and Western scholars have evaluated the actual efficacy of the TTB programs in generating the sort of innovation and intellectual development that the CCP sought. Numerous studies conducted have found that despite the enormous scale of China's talent programs, the PRC has fallen short of its stated objectives of recruiting the best to forward its scientific and technological development. While the PRC has managed to recruit more individuals to contribute to its national research, these individuals are not the so-called top caliber talents that the PRC are specifically looking for. As well, the recruited experts are not contributing a high volume of work to the PRC, nor is the PRC able to continue sustaining recruitment numbers to meet quotas.

A study published in the journal *Science* found that while the PRC has managed to recruit high quality scholars who are very productive in publication, these individuals are not the most elite or highest caliber of experts.²⁵ The PRC's incentives were unable to persuade the most experienced and most honored scientists to leave their prestigious jobs or even work

²³Original CSET Translation of "China Scholarship Council Subsidized Study Abroad Agreement" [资助出国留学协议书], Eddy's World Blog, January 2019, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/china-scholarship-council-subsidized-study-abroad-agreement/>; Original CSET Translation of "Detailed Rules for the Implementation of the 2016 "State Scholarship for Outstanding Self-Financed Study Abroad Students"" [2016 年“国家优秀自费留学生奖学金”实施细则], China Scholarship Council, July 9, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/detailed-rules-for-the-implementation-of-the-2016-state-scholarship-for-outstanding-self-financed-study-abroad-students/>.

²⁴Ryan Fedasiuk, "The China Scholarship Council: An Overview," Center for Security and Emerging Technology, July 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/the-china-scholarship-council:-an-overview/>.

²⁵Shi Dongbo, Liu Weichen, and Wang Yanbo, "Has China's Young Thousand Talents program been successful in recruiting and nurturing top-caliber scientists?" *Science* 379, no. 6627 (2023): 62-65, <https://www.science.org/doi/10.1126/science.abq1218>, p. 62.

part-time in China.²⁶ More than 85% of US-based Chinese STEM PhD students intend to stay in the United States, despite pressure from the China Scholarship Council and a 2019 sample of Chinese students working in the artificial intelligence field revealed that 78% of Chinese students who attended graduate school in the United States stayed in the US to work after graduation, despite AI expertise being in exceptionally high demand in the PRC.²⁷ Another sample notes that the rate of Chinese students staying in the United States after receiving AI Ph.Ds. from American universities floated around 90% from 2014-2018. Indeed, while the Chinese Ministry of Education reports the return of hundreds of thousands of Chinese students, many of China's best researchers prefer to remain abroad.²⁸ TTB programs then, are likely most attractive to middle-tier researchers for whom grant funding and prestigious positions in Western institutions is difficult to acquire.²⁹

As well, the productivity of recruited experts has also not quite been up to expectations. A bibliometric exploration of the TTB revealed that at its peak, the research produced by TTB affiliated experts only constituted at most 1% of the total research output in China.³⁰ Another study notes that while new hires from the Thousand Young Talents Program yielded an increased number of quality publications, the research output of the other faculty in Chinese institutions decreased after the introduction of Thousand Young Talents Program hires. Instead of these experts from overseas stimulating research, there seems to be a limited or even negative impact exerted on their colleagues' work. This same study also found that China's top 20 math departments saw little change in the hiring quality of scholars from highly ranked programs in other countries.³¹ There is also the pernicious issue of scholars regarding membership in the talent programs as a prize to be earned due to the growing prestige of these programs, and so they contribute their efforts to competing

²⁶Sun Yutao, Guo Rongyu, and Zhang Shuai, "China's Brain Gain at the High End: An Assessment of Thousand Youth Talents Program," *Asian Journal of Innovation and Policy* 6, no. 3 (2017): 274-294, <https://koreascience.kr/article/JAKO201712965729045.pdf>, p. 291-292.

²⁷William A. Carter and William D. Crumpler, "An Ecosystem Approach to AI Innovation," *Smart Money on Chinese Advances in AI*, Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), 2019, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep22599.8>, p. 8; Fedasiuk, "The China Scholarship Council: An Overview."

²⁸Remco Zwetsloot, "China's Approach to Tech Talent Competition: Policies, Results, and the Developing Global Response," Brookings Institution and Center for Security and Emerging Technology, April 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/chinas-approach-to-tech-talent-competition-policies-results-and-the-developing-global-response/>, p. 4-5.

²⁹Carter and Crumpler, "An Ecosystem Approach to AI Innovation," p. 8.

³⁰Ryan M. Allen and Yang L. Allen, "A Bibliometric Exploration into the Global Research Impact of China's Thousand Talents Brand," *Journal of Comparative and International Higher Education* 14, no. 5 (2022): 134-170, <https://www.ojed.org/index.php/jcihe/article/view/4581/2418>, p. 147, 160.

³¹Jia Ning and Belton Fleischer, "Economic Incentives and the Quality of Return Migrant Scholars: The Impact of China's Thousand Young Talents Program," *IZA Discussion Paper* No. 13073, March 30, 2020. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3562863>, 1-2, 22.

for a position in the programs and neglecting their teaching responsibilities and research, the opposite of what the programs were intended to do.³² All this to say, the benefits derived from TTB programs are not uniform, and fall short of the CCP's stated objectives.

It should also be noted that the talent programs themselves are inefficient in making recruiting numbers when not considering middle-caliber ethnic Chinese scholars. With regards to non-Chinese experts, only 390 scientists and engineers enrolled in the first ten years of the Thousand Foreign Talents Plan.³³ In 2018, the PRC's State Administration of Foreign Experts Affairs, responsible for recruiting foreign experts, was eliminated in a ministry reshuffle and its functions incorporated into the Ministry of Science and Technology due to poor performance making it unable to justify the costs it incurred.³⁴ A 2020 report from the Chinese Academy of Sciences also found that many CAS-affiliated recruitment units have not been efficient in outreach, with the number of potential applicants contacted and recommended by these units being rather low.³⁵ The fact that the talent procurement programs themselves have had structural issues in recruitment should come as no surprise, given the biggest impediment to scholar success and thus the TTB programs is also institutional.

A major complaint of experts who move to China to work, and one that has discouraged others from coming to China, is that there is a lack of intellectual freedom and stifling of innovation that hinders their work. This, in conjunction with the still-unrectified inconveniences that characterize living in China are what causes the recruitment programs to experience difficulties. Elite researchers are capable of getting the resources and support they need in the United States, without the air quality, food safety, family concerns, and lack of intellectual freedom that comes with living in China.³⁶ PRC scholars are not blind to this reality. A recurring trend in the advice given by Chinese intellectuals is that there needs to be a respect for an innovative spirit and more open-minded attitudes when dealing with

³²Zhu, "The Composition and Evolution of China's High-Level Talent Programs in Higher Education."

³³Zwetsloot, "China's Approach to Tech Talent Competition: Policies, Results, and the Developing Global Response," p. 6.

³⁴Original 2017 Budget of the Former State Administration of Foreign Experts Affairs [原国家外国专家局 2017 年度部门决算], PRC State Administration of Foreign Experts Affairs, July 20, 2018, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/research/2017-budget-of-the-former-state-administration-of-foreign-experts-affairs>.

³⁵Original CSET Translation of "Situation Report on CAS' Work on the "Youth Thousand Talents Program" [我院“青年千人计划”工作情况通报], Bureau of Personnel and Education [人事教育局] of the Chinese Academy of Sciences [CAS; 中国科学院], June 29, 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/publication/situation-report-on-cas-work-on-the-youth-thousand-talents-program/>, p. 5.

³⁶William A. Carter and William D. Crumpler, "An Ecosystem Approach to AI Innovation," p. 8.

scholars who came from abroad.³⁷ Other PRC scholars also advocate for the expansion of programs and collaborations in funding and scope, noting that at present, the current resources are insufficient to overcome the bureaucratic roadblocks to living and working in China.³⁸ For their part, the talented experts themselves, have expressed frustration at their stagnating careers, finding themselves to be the outgroup among their colleagues who were originally working in China, and thus their abilities are not employed well.³⁹ The recruited experts do not have the requisite connections to navigate a system dominated by *guanxi* [關係], a Chinese word that literally means ‘relationships’ and used to describe the phenomenon of nepotism and cronyism that persists in the PRC.⁴⁰ Cognizant of this, PRC intellectuals studying talent procurement have advised the government to fast-track the TTBB recruited individuals into leadership positions and/or form all-star teams composed of

³⁷Huang Rihan [黄日涵], Yao Haolong [姚浩龙], "A Reshaped World? New Features of Artificial Intelligence and National Security under the Rise of ChatGPT [被重塑的世界? ChatGPT 崛起下人工智能与国家安全新特征]", CSIS Interpret: China, original work published in *Journal of International Security Studies* [国际安全研究], June 28, 2023, <https://interpret.csis.org/translations/a-reshaped-world-new-features-of-artificial-intelligence-and-national-security-under-the-rise-of-chatgpt/>; Shang Qianming [尚前名], "How Should China Build a Modernized Superpower? [建设现代化强国, 中国应该怎么做?]", CSIS Interpret: China, original work published in *Xinhua Outlook Weekly* [瞭望周刊社], March 1, 2021, <https://interpret.csis.org/translations/how-should-china-build-a-modernized-superpower/>; He Jun [贺俊], "Critical Dimensions and Strategic Points for Building a Manufacturing Power [制造强国建设的关键维度和战略要点]", CSIS Interpret: China, original work published in *Reform* [改革], March 2, 2021, <https://interpret.csis.org/translations/critical-dimensions-and-strategic-points-for-building-a-manufacturing-power/>.

³⁸Guo Tianqiang [田国强], "Suggestions on establishing a long-term mechanism for the introduction of overseas high-level and cutting-edge talents [关于建立海外高层次尖端人才引进长效机制的建议]", School of Economics, Institute for Advanced Study, Shanghai University of Finance and Economics [上海财经大学经济学院、高等研究院], February 28, 2012, <https://people.tamu.edu/~gtian/tian-policy-10-1.pdf>; Chen Zhi [陈志], "Strategic thinking and suggestions for the introduction of overseas high-end talents [引进海外高端人才战略思考与建议]", *Science and Technology China* [科技中国] (2021) Issue 9, pgs 56-58, September 26, 2021, <http://www.casted.org.cn/channel/newsinfo/8367>; 贺俊 (He Jun), "Critical Dimensions and Strategic Points for Building a Manufacturing Power [制造强国建设的关键维度和战略要点]".

³⁹Zwetsloot, "China's Approach to Tech Talent Competition: Policies, Results, and the Developing Global Response," p. 5.

⁴⁰Li Chunhao, Wang Chengsi, Wu Lei, et. al., "The Impact of International Talent Inflow on Technological Innovation: The Moderating Role of Guanxi Culture and Social Trust," *Sage Open*, 14(3), September 9, 2024, <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241268801>.

largely TTB experts, to mitigate the pernicious effect that *guanxi* has on talent retention and employment.⁴¹

Potential Threat that Talent Procurement Programs Pose and Countermeasures

Despite these findings, members of the US security establishment remain concerned about the potential for insider threat. Several professionals subscribe to the view that the PRC is employing a “thousand grains of sand” approach, whereby the CCP recruits whoever it can, wherever it can, and collectively the efforts of all these informants would provide the PRC with a massive trove of confidential and proprietary information.⁴² Testimony to Congress reveals that a not insignificant number of TTB affiliated researchers work in fields of science that have military utility, and that recruitment efforts have disproportionately focused on individuals who held positions in US government agencies that deal with sensitive technological information.⁴³ More specifically, Congress’s Select Committee on the CCP claims that US publications with PRC connections covered topics with direct military applications, potentially advancing the PRC in fourth-generation nuclear weapon systems, artificial intelligence for the military applications, lasers, semiconductors, and robotics.⁴⁴ Particularly worrisome to the United States is the fact that many of these recruiters and collaboration efforts have ties to universities in China known as the “Seven Sons of National Defense,” institutions that actively carry out research on behalf of China’s People’s Liberation Army.⁴⁵ For instance, in 2020, a PLA officer was indicted for attempted theft of

⁴¹Cui Leilei [崔磊磊], Du Xiangwan [杜祥琬], Qin Ge [葛琴], et. al., “Macro Research on the Development of Chinese Strategic Emerging Industries in the New Era [新时期我国战略性新兴产业发展宏观研究]”, CSIS Interpret: China, original work published in Strategic Study of CAE [中国工程科学], March 27, 2020, <https://interpret.csis.org/translations/macro-research-on-the-development-of-chinese-strategic-emerging-industries-in-the-new-era/>; Guo [田], “Suggestions on establishing a long-term mechanism for the introduction of overseas high-level and cutting-edge talents [关于建立海外高层次尖端人才引进长效机制的建议]”; Chen [陈], “Strategic thinking and suggestions for the introduction of overseas high-end talents [引进海外高端人才战略思考与建议]”.

⁴²John Poreba, “Neutralizing China’s Student-Spy Network,” *International Journal of Intelligence and Counterintelligence* 25, no. 2 (2012): 260-291, <https://sci-hub.se/10.1080/08850607.2012.623037>, p. 264.

⁴³US Senate Staff, “Threats to the U.S. Research Enterprise: China’s Talent Recruitment Plans,” p. 2, 4-5, 7-8, 14.

⁴⁴U.S. House of Representatives Staff, “CCP on the Quad: How American Taxpayers and Universities Fund the CCP’s Advanced Military and Technological Research,” United States House of Representatives Select Committee on the CCP, September 23, 2024, [https://selectcommitteeontheccp.house.gov/media/reports/ccp-quad-how-american-taxpayers-and-universities-fund-ccps-advanced-military-and#:~:text=The%20Chinese%20Communist%20Party%20\(CCP\)%20exploits%20federally%20funded%20research%20and](https://selectcommitteeontheccp.house.gov/media/reports/ccp-quad-how-american-taxpayers-and-universities-fund-ccps-advanced-military-and#:~:text=The%20Chinese%20Communist%20Party%20(CCP)%20exploits%20federally%20funded%20research%20and), p. 1-2.

⁴⁵US Senate Staff, “Threats to the U.S. Research Enterprise: China’s Talent Recruitment Plans,” p. 89.

biological research, with access made possible by a professor participating in the Thousand Talents Plan.⁴⁶ As well, the Australian Strategic Policy Institute finds that some TTB-affiliated researchers have been rewarded for providing the PRC with stolen technology and that Chinese intelligence officers have had a hand in TTB recruitment.⁴⁷ In facilitating this knowledge transfer and emplacement of assets, visa fraud has become a frequently used tactic for bringing in facilitators for talent recruitment programs with indictments made in 2019-2021. In all these cases, those arrested had ties to the PLA or intelligence apparatus, with one individual was a visiting researcher at Stanford University.⁴⁸ The realized concern is that US funds are being funneled towards individuals who would use them to pursue research that might threaten US national security and steal vital information from the US.⁴⁹

While it is not illegal under US law to be affiliated with such talent procurement programs and researchers frequently collaborate across international borders, the terms of the TTB contracts incentivize illicit activity.⁵⁰ A US Senate report finds that many contracts presented to recruits contain nondisclosure agreements, which only allow researchers to share their work with China, and only the Chinese government can terminate this agreement.⁵¹ Where this becomes problematic is the fact that much of these experts' work is also funded by US government entities and in some cases, the research is classified.⁵² Dr.

⁴⁶CSIS Strategic Technologies Program, "A Survey of Chinese Espionage in the United States Since 2000," Center for Strategic and International Studies, March 2023, <https://www.csis.org/programs/strategic-technologies-program/survey-chinese-espionage-united-states-2000>, p. 15.

⁴⁷Alex Joske, "Hunting the Phoenix: The Chinese Communist Party's Global Search for Technology and Talent," Australian Strategic Policy Institute, https://ad-aspi.s3.ap-southeast-2.amazonaws.com/2020-10/Hunting%20the%20phoenix_v2.pdf?VersionId=TX_kD_pNKIBF.xuSdZO1UMuTKmiNEeAK, p. 5.

⁴⁸Ibid., p. 15-16, 18.

⁴⁹Jeffrey Stoff and Glenn Tiffert, "Under the Radar: National Security Risk in US-China Scientific Collaboration," In *Global Engagement: Rethinking Risk in the Research Enterprise*, edited by Glenn Tiffert, 19-104, Stanford: Hoover Institution, https://www.hoover.org/sites/default/files/research/docs/tiffert_globalengagement_ch1-0805_0.pdf, p. 22, 32.

⁵⁰Shawna A. Matthys, "China's Hidden Talent: The Thousand Talent Plan," *Air University Wild Blue Yonder Online Journal*, October 26, 2023, <https://www.airuniversity.af.edu/Wild-Blue-Yonder/Articles/Article-Display/Article/3541536/chinas-hidden-talent-the-thousand-talent-plan/>.

⁵¹US Senate Staff, "Threats to the U.S. Research Enterprise: China's Talent Recruitment Plans," p. 2, 31-32.

⁵²Kathleen M. Vogel and Sonia Ben Ouagrham-Gormley, "Scientists as Spies?: Assessing U.S. Claims about the Security Threat Posed by China's Thousand Talents Program for the U.S. Life

Song Guo Zheng, a former professor at Ohio State University, was found guilty of deliberately hiding funds from talent programs and wrote that he intended to “bring back several innovative products and conduct clinical transformation of the products in hopes to develop China’s brand in the biomedical area.”⁵³ A professional in the field of syntactic foam, a material crucial for submarines, applied to talent programs stating their intentions to “digest” and “absorb” the relevant technology from the United States.⁵⁴ What compounds this issue is that many TTB affiliated researchers do not disclose their involvement in these programs, additionally constituting a form of employment fraud.⁵⁵ In one such high profile case, Dr. Charles Lieber, the former chair of Harvard’s Chemistry Department and a pioneer in nanotechnology, was convicted for withholding information about funding from China’s Wuhan University.⁵⁶ In addition, a professor at Texas A&M University who had NASA grants and access to classified projects was found guilty in 2020 for not disclosing his participation in the Thousand Talents Plan.⁵⁷

The idea that the PRC is attempting to use academic collaboration as a conduit for obtaining highly sensitive information and technologies has received pushback from other sections of academia studying this topic. A study from the University of California at San Diego notes that Communist Party officials were largely preoccupied with establishing collaborations and partnerships, and not actually evaluating them for tangible results.⁵⁸ In addition, the Center for Security and Emerging Technology finds that only 8.3% of researchers with ties to the Young Thousand Talents Program have any connection to one of the “Seven Sons of National Defense.” While the CSET concedes that it is uncertain if this trend holds up with the broader Thousand Talents Program, it estimates that no more than 100 of the thousands recruited would have such ties to the PLA and that many of these participants

Sciences,” *Politics and the Life Sciences* 42, no. 1 (2023): 32–64, <https://doi.org/10.1017/pls.2022.13>, p. 44-48.

⁵³Aundrea Sandfort, “AN EVALUATION OF THE UNITED STATES GOVERNMENT’S EFFECTIVENESS ON ACADEMIC INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY SECURITY,” Johns Hopkins University Scholarship Library, May 16, 2022, <https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/server/api/core/bitstreams/795d168c-0a1f-4582-b4ff-95cd64c4046e/content>, p. 27-28.

⁵⁴Anthony H. Cordesman and Grace Hwang. “Shifting from Competition to Confrontation,” in *U.S. Competition with China and Russia: The Crisis-Driven Need to Change U.S. Strategy*, Center for Strategic and International Studies (CSIS), 2020, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep25689.13>, p. 120.

⁵⁵Matthys, “China’s Hidden Talent: The Thousand Talent Plan.”

⁵⁶Beryl Lieff Benderly, “CHINA SYNDROME,” *ASEE Prism* 29, no. 8 (2020): 28–31, <https://www.jstor.org/stable/26920114>, p. 29.

⁵⁷CSIS Strategic Technologies Program, “A Survey of Chinese Espionage in the United States Since 2000,” p. 16.

⁵⁸Fan Yang, “Surveying China’s Science and Technology Human Talents Programs,” *SITC Research Briefs* no. 3, 2015, <https://escholarship.org/content/qt5qg340x3/qt5qg340x3.pdf>, p. 5.

would have been trained outside of the United States anyway.⁵⁹ Still others insist that knowledge transfer in the way that US officials suggest is not so easy to facilitate, and it requires much more than simply collaborating on a project or even having blueprints to effectively utilize confidential and proprietary information.⁶⁰ The National Institutes of Health's Deputy Director for Extramural Research, Michael Lauer, doesn't characterize the TTB itself as a threat, rather, he claims the problem is with the failure to disclose it.⁶¹ It is worth noting that instances of IP and technology theft are rare and that most of those affiliated with the Thousand Talents Program are arrested because they did not disclose their dual affiliation with the US and China. Thus, they commit fraud and misappropriate funds rather than actually stealing secrets.⁶²

Regardless of the success of the PRC's talent programs, real or perceived, there is no denying the fact that they have become a mechanism by which illicit activity is facilitated and encouraged in some cases. The illegal activity can take the form of insider threat, with potentially grave implications for US national security. Understanding the issue at hand is critical, not only for protecting US interests, but also for preserving the integrity of academia and the spirit of international research cooperation. The presence of the TTB programs has cast doubt on research collaboration which would otherwise be mutually beneficial for all parties involved.

Various US government entities have worked to mitigate the TTB's potential threat. The Congress's Select Committee on the CCP suggested adapting the DETERRENT Act, which would require further transparency from universities and researchers of foreign contracts

⁵⁹Ryan Fedasiuk and Jacob Feldgoise, "The Youth Thousand Talents Plan and China's Military," Center for Security and Emerging Technology, August 2020, <https://cset.georgetown.edu/wp-content/uploads/CSET-Youth-Thousand-Talents-Plan-and-Chinas-Military.pdf>, p. 11.

⁶⁰Vogel and Ouagrham-Gormley, "Scientists as Spies?: Assessing U.S. Claims about the Security Threat Posed by China's Thousand Talents Program for the U.S. Life Sciences," p.48-53.

⁶¹National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine; Division on Engineering and Physical Sciences; Health and Medicine Division; Policy and Global Affairs; Division on Earth and Life Studies; Forum on Cyber Resilience; Board on Health Sciences Policy; Board on Science, Technology, and Economic Policy; Board on Agriculture and Natural Resources; Board on Life Sciences; Committee on Safeguarding the Bioeconomy: Finding Strategies for Understanding, Evaluating, and Protecting the Bioeconomy While Sustaining Innovation and Growth, *Safeguarding the Bioeconomy*, Washington (DC): National Academies Press (US); 2020 Jan 14. 7, ECONOMIC AND NATIONAL SECURITY RISKS PERTAINING TO THE BIOECONOMY, <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK556435/>.

⁶²David Zweig and Siqin Kang, "America Challenges China's National Talent Programs," Center for Strategic and International Studies, May 2020, https://csis-website-prod.s3.amazonaws.com/s3fs-public/publication/20505_zweig_AmericaChallenges_v6_FINAL.pdf, p. 1-2, 12.

and better enable the identification of potential insider threats.⁶³ From the Executive branch, the National Security Presidential Memorandum, NSPM-33, was devised to maintain open research and innovative environments while strengthening the protections of US government-supported innovations. This led to the implementation of policies regarding transparency in disclosure and information sharing, as well as strengthening security programs. In addition, it implemented Digital Persistent Identifiers, which are used to identify individuals.⁶⁴ Government entities like the National Institutes of Health and National Science Foundation have implemented NSPM-33 and have focused on implementing new requirements for transparency. In addition to this, in the application process, the NIH elaborated more to include sections where applicants can identify themselves if they are related to any foreign government programs.⁶⁵ Other perspectives on the issue suggest potential grant restrictions in federally funded research or potential visa restrictions for those with clear connections to the PRC.⁶⁶

Conclusion

Understanding the methodology, efficacy, and perceived threat of the PRC's talent procurement programs is crucial in identifying ways to mitigate its success. U.S. policymakers will be tasked with identifying the most effective way to mitigate insider threats while supporting the advancement of research and collaboration. For now, vigilance through further education on the issue serves to mitigate the ambiguity that creates problems surrounding the talent programs and incentivizes bad behavior.

⁶³U.S. House of Representatives Staff, "CCP on the Quad: How American Taxpayers and Universities Fund the CCP's Advanced Military and Technological Research," p. 3.

⁶⁴Aundrea Sandfort, "AN EVALUATION OF THE UNITED STATES GOVERNMENT'S EFFECTIVENESS ON ACADEMIC INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY SECURITY," p. 30-32.

⁶⁵Ibid., p.43-45.

⁶⁶ Zwetsloot, "China's Approach to Tech Talent Competition: Policies, Results, and the Developing Global Response," p. 8.

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